

MECHANIZATION OF THE PROCESS OF DESTRUCTION OF THE TRANSVERSE PAWLS IN BETWEEN COTTON ROWS

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Abstract: In this article, the issue of mechanization of the technological process of breaking the transverse furrows among cotton rows, which is done by hand until today, is studied, and the device for breaking the furrows through the working bodies of the cultivator is proposed and its advantages are presented.

Key words: Longitudinal and transverse furrows, threshing unit, cultivator working bodies, device that destroys transverse furrows, productivity, energy saving.

ҒЎЗА ҚАТОР ОРАЛАРИДАГИ КЎНДАЛАНГ ПОЛЛАРНИ БУЗИШ ЖАРАЁНИНИ МЕХАНИЗАЦИЯЛАШ

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада бугунги кунга қадар қўл кучи билан бажарилиб келинаётган ғўза қаторлари орасида кўндаланг полларни бузиш технология жараёнини механизациялаш масаласи ўрганилган ва культиватор иш органлари орқали полларни бузиш бўйича қурилма таклиф этилган ва унинг афзалликлари келтирилган.

Калит сўзлар: Бўйлама ва кўндаланг поллар, чопиқ агрегати, культиватор иш органлари, кўндаланг полларни бузадиган қурилма, иш унуми, энергиятежамкорлик.

Introduction: The irrigated lands in the cotton-growing areas of our republic are divided into three regions according to the natural-climate and soil conditions, the mechanical composition of the soil, the technology of tillage and the types of machines used, the agrotechnical requirements imposed on them. Before the first irrigation in the cotton-growing regions with saline soil (Bukhara, Navoi, Khorezm, Kashkadarya regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan), longitudinal and transverse furrows are formed between the rows due to the slope of the field and its relative unevenness (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. An irrigated field forming longitudinal and transverse furrows between rows of cotton

Statement of issue: Longitudinal furrows are formed once per irrigation period of cotton, while transverse furrows are formed before all irrigations and are broken up during inter-row tillage after irrigations. The fact that these technological processes are carried out by hand until today is the reason for the increase in the cost of manual labor and other costs in cotton cultivation and the decrease in the level of mechanization.

After irrigation of the cotton fields, it will not be possible to perform quality treatment between the rows without destroying the cross furrows. Because if the transverse furrows are not damaged, the stable operation of the cultivator working bodies in terms of the working depth will deteriorate, the loads on the working bodies will increase, and as a result, their deformation and breakage will be observed. For this reason, after each watering, the transverse furrows are broken up and cultivated between the rows with a cultivator.

It is necessary to create transverse furrows together with longitudinal furrows in cotton fields with uneven relief. This serves to ensure that water is supplied to the cotton plants in an equal amount and that water is evenly distributed at the beginning

and end points of the field (that is, cotton plants are not submerged in water in some uneven places). Another advantage of this method is that by using it, the cotton crop does not get flooded.

Currently, it is known that longitudinal furrowing is done in a mechanized way with the help of longitudinal threshing devices aggregated to TTZ 80K11, LS-100, T-28X4 tractors [1]. In Uzbekistan, depending on the soil and climatic conditions, technological processes such as forming cross-furrows before each irrigation and breaking cross-furrows before cultivation are carried out during the full vegetation period of cotton cultivation in order to treat cotton seedlings in cultivated fields. Based on this, it is necessary to create and destroy cross furrows 4-5 times in one season.

To date, furrow-breaking machines are used in the fields for breaking the longitudinal and transverse furrows taken for salt washing in the fall, that is, tractors, bulldozers and motor graders adapted to break the longitudinal and transverse furrows created for washing the salt of the field in open areas, but these machines cannot be used to break the transverse furrows formed for watering cotton between the rows.

Based on this, every time after watering, cultivation in the cotton fields requires the transverse furrows in the cotton fields be broken by manual labor due to the fact that they hinder the movement of the tractors, and after cultivation, it is required to create the transverse furrows again by hand for subsequent watering of the cotton field. This process is carried out between each watering and cultivation process. Based on this, the high cost of labor in the technological process causes an increase in the price of the product in cotton cultivation.

A way to solve the problem: Taking into account the above, scientific and research work is being carried out on the mechanization of the processes of forming and breaking transverse furrows. The problem is solved by installing transverse furrow-breaking sections, one in front of its front wheel and one in front of the front working bodies of the cultivator, located side by side at a distance L from each other along each row and raised and lowered by a hydraulic cylinder [2] (Fig. 2) .

Figure 2. Constructive scheme of the device that destroys transverse furrows.

The transverse furrow-breaking section consists of a cross-furrow frame 8 mounted on the front mounting device mounted on the tractor's spars, a parallelogram mechanism 1 attached to the reducer, a bar attached to it 2, a support wheel attached to it 6, and flat softening pawls 3 mounted stepwise through the columns and the one-sided right and left arrow-shaped claws 4 and the double-sided arrow-shaped claw 5 in the middle, and the whole unit is five furrow-breaking sections located side by side at a distance L from each other, installed in front of the front wheel of the tractor, and all through a separate cylinder 7 is raised and lowered simultaneously with the working bodies of the cultivator between the rows.

Cross-furrow breaking sections work in the following order. As the tractor moves across the row for post-irrigation between cotton rows, it breaks the cross-furrow R_s in layers through five breaker sections. When breaking the transverse furrows between the rows of cotton, the floor-breaking sections are raised and lowered by the hydraulic cylinder 7 in the frame 8 with a transverse brush, so that the device breaks the transverse furrows layer by layer in front of the working bodies of the cultivator, and the stable movement of the front and rear wheels of the tractor between the rows is ensured. Then the working organs of the cultivator are ensured to work smoothly [3].

In this process, an experimental version of the working equipment for demolishing transverse furrows was developed and field experiments were conducted. In this case, an additional working device is installed on the front part of the front wheel of the tractor and on the right and left half frames of the cultivator (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Transverse furrow demolition device

Results and samples: A theoretical calculation was performed to determine the longitudinal distance between the arrow-shaped and softening claws of the working body of the device. We find the longitudinal distance between the arrow-shaped and softening paws, provided that the soil does not get stuck between them. Figure 4 shows that this condition is fulfilled.

4 – picture. The scheme for determining the longitudinal distance between the arrow-shaped and softening claws

As can be seen from the diagram, the distance l between the ends of the arrow-shaped and softening claws should be greater than the horizontal projection AB' of the fracture line AB of the soil under the action of the arrow-shaped claw, i.e.

$$l \geq AB' = h \operatorname{ctg} \psi_{\sigma}, \tag{1}$$

where h – arrow-shaped and softening claws are the vertical (vertical) distance, m ; ψ_{σ} - refraction angle of the soil in the longitudinal direction, $^{\circ}$.

It is known [4]

$$\psi_{\sigma} = \frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{\alpha_0 + \varphi_1 + \varphi_2}{2}, \tag{2}$$

Here, α_0 - the angle of penetration of the arrow-shaped claw into the soil, °.

α_0 - the angle can be found by the following expression [5]

$$\alpha_0 = \arctg (tg \alpha \cdot \sin \gamma) \quad (3)$$

Taking into account expressions (2) and (3), expression (1) will have the following form

$$l \geq h tg \frac{\arctg(tg \alpha \cdot \sin \gamma) + \varphi_1 + \varphi_2}{2}. \quad (4)$$

(4) taking into account the expression, we find the longitudinal distance L between the arrow-shaped and softening paws from the following expression

$$L = l_q + h tg \frac{\arctg(tg \alpha \cdot \sin \gamma) + \varphi_1 + \varphi_2}{2}, \quad (5)$$

here l_q is the length of the part of the arrow-shaped paw protruding from the column, m;

From this expression, it can be seen that the longitudinal distance between the arrow-shaped and softening paws depends on the vertical distance between their ends, the angles of the wings of the arrow-shaped paw and the angles of external and internal friction of the soil.

$l_q = 10$ cm; $h = 10$ cm; $\alpha = 25^\circ$; $\gamma = 30^\circ$; $\varphi_1 = 25^\circ$; $\varphi_2 = 35^\circ$ assuming that according to expression (5), we find that the longitudinal distance between the arrow-shaped and softening paws is not less than 18 cm.

After irrigation, in combination with inter-row processing of cotton, due to full mechanization of breaking transverse furrows, economic efficiency will increase several times, reduce manual labor and reduce the cost of cotton cultivation.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be noted that, taking into account the high importance of transverse furrows in cotton cultivation, it is considered urgent to reduce the cost of the product by fully mechanizing the technological process of creating and breaking transverse furrows, and at the same time, to reduce labor costs through the mechanization of manual labor. In the process of cultivation of transverse furrows without additional work, works are being carried out on the creation of the technology

of execution through an additional device adapted to the working bodies of the cultivator, which is aggregated on the base of the tractor.

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